

REAL LIFE EXPERIENCES IN NATHANIEL HAWTHORNE'S WORKS

Rakhmanova Viktoriya

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

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INTRODUCTION

Real life experiences are essential in literature because they are the foundation of what makes it enduring, relevant, and powerful. Real life experiences are crucial to literature for the following reasons:

Universality: Real emotions like love, grief, treachery, happiness, and difficulty are universal in nature. Readers from many origins, eras, and cultures may relate to these issues. Through delving into these core experiences, literature serves as a bridge that unites people from different backgrounds and help hem discover points of agreement.

Emotional resonance: Readers moved frequently to tears by literature that explore important real experiences. Readers are able to form a strong emotional bond with characters who are experiencing comparable hardships or victories, which can have a long-lasting effect.

Understanding the real condition: Literature may help us understand the complexity of the real situation. Through in-depth examination of pivotal real events, writers may illuminate the incentives, longings, apprehensions, and goals that shape human conduct. Readers may better comprehend themselves and the intricacies of life by gaining a greater insight of human nature.

Catharsis: Both the writer and the reader may find catharsis in writing about real events. People can find relief, healing, and closure by using storytelling to tackle challenging emotions and experiences. This cathartic process has the potential to be transforming and restorative.

Real life experiences are fundamental to literature because they provide the framework for gripping narratives, deep understanding of the human condition, and emotional resonance. Literature is an essential tool for examining what it is to be human since it may inspire, challenge, reassure, and stimulate readers via the exploration of these universal themes. Every human experience has meaning. In actuality, writing also has the ability to immortalize trivial human events.

THE SCARLET LETTER

Nathaniel Hawthorne was born in 4th July in 1804 and was died in 19th May in 1864. He wrote novels and short stories. His literary works delivered the message about religion, morality and history. His family lived in Salem, Massachusetts, where he was born and they lived there for a long time there. He

entered the college of Bowdoin then he was elected to Phi Beta Kappa in 1824. After a year he received his degree. Fanshawe is his first book which was released in 1828. Next, he decided to publish his work. In 1837 he wrote a number of additional short stories into his Twice-Told Tales. He asked Sophia Peabody to marry him in 1842. Having worked at the Boston Custom House he joined Brook. He joined to the transcendentalist team of Brook

Farm and worked at the Boston Custom House before he got married to Peabody in the same year when he asked her to marry him. Firstly they lived in Concord, Massachusetts' The Old Manse. After a couple of years they leave for Salem in the Berkshires, and again they moved back to their initial location. In 1850, a number of fresh books were published after the publication of The Scarlet Letter. Hawthorne's family had worked as political appointment as counsels, then they traveled through Europe. They come back to Concord in 1860. Hawthorne was passed away in 19th May in 1864.

Nathaniel Hawthorne's novel The Scarlet Letter is can be a vivid example of one of his works as he used his real life experiences in this novel. "A writer should include all of his premises and overviews and of course his own experiences in his works" says Gustave Flaubert. Due to his heritage of Puritan Hawthorne had an unusual perspective about people in Puritan and controlled the setting of The Scarlet Letter. His great desire toward reading classic literature had influenced in his works. According to the collections of his mother and his initial years Hawthorne gave a strong and lovely image of Hester in The Scarlet Letter. Pearl is one of the character in his works who was the effect of his later life. Characters such as evil, pride, free choice and fate, guilt, the dark side of human nature were the central theme in his novels.

The Scarlet Letter was the inspiration of the history and experience of Hawthorne's family. The main reason is that he tried to portray a real image of the times through portraying a real location and accurate philosophies, he wrote on his own experiences. The writer tried to dedicate his life to literature and was solitary person. He lived in New England as he became an adult. There is the descriptive sentence toward Hawthorne by Robert Spiller. "We can imagine New England without Hawthorne. However, we can not see the Hawthorne without New England" Robert Spiller claims. As a result, Hawthorne's real life and his writings were coincides with New England's

culture. Because of the effect The Scarlet Letter was set by Hawthorne in the early New England colony. He described the setting as a time in the history of New England.

Those discrete components gathered together to create The Scarlet Letter. As the author included his opinions and real experiences in his novel, readers were able to be closer to the atmosphere in the novel. As a result, The Scarlet Letter became one of the famous works in literature of America.

According to the Gustave Flaubert “The author be like God is over the universe in his writings present everywhere and invisible nowhere”. One of the common activity between fiction writers is the expression of their own ideas and opinions in their novels. The Scarlet Letter by Nathaniel Hawthorne is one of the book which is written according to the author’s real life experiences. This book is one of the famous novel that describes Puritan life. The protagonist in this novel is Hester Prynne. She wear the red letter “A” on her chest to display her shame to the folk. She lives her whole life by paying for her sins. The book is the first example that portrays the hard lifestyle of Puritan. This book is a vivid examination of never-ending fight with pride, guilt and sin of human nature. The Scarlet Letter shows Hawthorne’s own beliefs by different themes.

CONCLUSION

It is difficult to imagine literature without real life experiences. As the literature is a reflected by reality, success is the result of real life experiences. The Scarlet Letter by Nathaniel Hawthorne is given as an example as it describes the judgements that people faced in their everyday life. In addition, there is shown the real life in New England. The special part of life of Hawthorne was spent on to reject the Puritans. Because, he never liked the way that the problems are tackled. So, The Scarlet Letter was the result of the author’s premises toward Puritans.

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